

ENRICHING SCIENCE SEARCH WITH THE OPEN SEARCH FRAMEWORK MOSAIC

A. Nussbaumer¹
¹Graz University of Technology, Graz, Austria
²German Aerospace Center, Cologne, Germany

Abstract

This paper presents a concept how the search in digital science libraries can be enriched with contextual science information. Digital science libraries often consist of collections of scientific publications that can be explored and searched in a structured way by using metadata to search and filter. We propose a concept of how the search can be extended with web content that includes related information, such as conferences, researchers, research projects, research data, or general knowledge on the topic. Thus, contextual information not included in a digital library can be added to a search result. This concept is demonstrated by an application in the field of earth observation that integrates earth observation catalogues with web content related to environmental emergency events.

INTRODUCTION

Digital libraries are important in the academic field, as they enable users and especially researchers to search and find scientific publications. Their core functionalities include the storage and digital objects and a retrieval system for the stored objects [1]. Digital libraries in the science field can be classified according to the operator or publisher, the amount, and topical domain of the digital publications they offer. For example, university libraries offer books and publications in the fields relevant to the institution. Journals and scientific publishers offer their published content. General digital libraries, such as Google Scholar, have indexed scientific literature available at other digital libraries.

Basic features of digital libraries include effectiveness (hosting of required documents), efficiency (retrieval accuracy), accessibility (low access barriers), usability, software quality, and satisfactory (meeting the users' information need) [1]. Information retrieval and indexing key information is an essential issue of digital libraries [2]. Furthermore, the semantic web and social networking technologies help improve the usage of digital libraries [3].

Scientific Digital Library Systems aim to manage, search, and retrieve scientific data, such as publications, research data, and other scientific outcomes. Usually, they contain digital objects that have been approved and created in the past. In contrast, web data related to science contain more recent and up-to-date information, such as events and news. However, researchers often need information from both scientific publications and active research activities. Thus, it becomes obvious that these types of information should be combined into an integrated system where the user can search and retrieve all types of information.

In order to address this issue, this paper presents an approach and implementation that enriches the search in digital libraries with information from the web related to the knowledge domain of the digital library. The main contribution of this paper consists in a concept based on semantic information and metadata that connects digital libraries with web-based information sources and increases efficiency and user satisfaction in the search process.

SCIENCE SEARCH ENRICHMENT

The Modular Search Application Based on Index Fraction (MOSAIC) [4] is a framework and generic search application that makes index partitions searchable. Index partitions are small or medium sized indices containing web documents related to a certain topic or for a particular purpose. These partitions are being created using the OpenWebSearch.eu infrastructure and contain various metadata, such as geo-coordinates, topics, and genres of the web documents [5]. MOSAIC is built upon the Prototype Search Application [6] and provides an Application Programming Interface (API) to search index partitions and to filter the results according to the above mentioned metadata.

The overall approach of integrating scientific digital libraries with web search is depicted in Figure 1. On the one hand, an existing digital library system is used that provides an API for searching and retrieving digital objects. On the other hand, the MOSAIC framework is used to make web content available in the search and retrieval process. On a conceptual level the integration is realised by connecting search results with joint metadata.

Figure 1: Conceptual design of science search context.

The selection of the joint metadata depends on the metadata provided by the digital library. Typical metadata of scientific digital libraries are author, date, and keywords of publications, but also geographic and temporal information. In order to semantically join search results by metadata, the same description language must be supported by MOSAIC. Either respective metadata are provided by datasets from the Open Web Index (OWI) or they have to be generated in a pre-processing step. Currently, the OWI datasets provide geo-locations and domain topics.

Metadata handling in MOSAIC

The management of metadata in MOSAIC is conceptually built around a modular architecture, which allows for the separation of concerns and the independent processing of different metadata aspects. Central to this system are various specialised modules, each designed to handle distinct types of metadata. This modular design, technically realised using Apache Maven modules, allows users to enable or disable modules easily via a configuration file.

In MOSAIC, metadata is utilised through a dual approach involving metadata filtering and enrichment. Metadata filtering allows users to apply specific criteria to refine search results based on metadata columns of the OWI partition. This process can be executed directly using the metadata columns or through more advanced algorithms, which leverage specific metadata columns for sophisticated filtering. Once the filtering is complete, MOSAIC enriches the search results from the Lucene index by adding the specified metadata. In its current version, MOSAIC encompasses various modules which function within a structured API framework to facilitate interaction with the central index and search components.

The *core* module in the MOSAIC framework manages fundamental metadata fields such as document titles, URLs, and languages. It ensures that basic information is consistently available for all search results. This module interacts with other specialised modules, and provides a foundation for further metadata processing. Geographical metadata is managed by the existing *geo module*, which enriches search results with detailed location-based information. This module includes metadata fields for locations such as coordinates, location names, and administrative regions. For instance, a search result might include the exact latitude and longitude of a place, the city or region name. Filtering is achieved through a bounding box mechanism, where users specify the western, eastern, northern, and southern boundaries to limit search results to a specific geographic area. Additionally, the geographical information is represented in the search results to offer users a clear spatial context that enhances the relevance of the data. Eventually, the *keywords* module focuses on integrating relevant keywords extracted from the full text of the respective document.

Additional metadata can be incorporated by either extending an existing module if it aligns thematically or creating a new metadata module. If the new metadata is related to an existing module's theme, it can be added by updating the

module's configuration and processing logic. Alternatively, users can define a new module that specifies the additional metadata fields and processing logic required. If filtering using the additional metadata is desired, users need to handle the processing of HTTP query parameters, particularly when the filtering goes beyond straightforward equality comparisons. Subsequently, advanced filtering logic can be implemented by overriding the provided methods if necessary. Moreover, to include additional metadata columns in search results, they must be specified in the module, with advanced processing for enrichment implemented as needed.

A simple web interface demonstrating the use of metadata with MOSAIC is shown in Figure 2. Beside a search term, the user can enter a geographic region and keywords to filter the search result. The geographic filter allows to specify a geographic rectangle using longitudinal and latitudinal boundaries. The location information (coordinates) of the indexed web documents is used to filter the search result, so that only documents show up in the result that have locations within the specified geographic rectangle. Similarly, the user can specify keywords that are used to compare and filter web documents that have keywords in their metadata. The web documents in the search result include both geographic locations and keywords.

Search term: Italy [Search]

Geo Filter: West: 2 East: 17 North: 55

Index: default / all Demo SimpleWiki Demo Graz Universities DLR Prototype

Language: default / all English German

Limit: default / 20 10 items 50 items 1,000,000

Keyword: floods

Search URL: https://qnode.eu/ows/mosaic/service/search?q=Italy&index=dlrprototype&keyword=floods&west=2&east=17&north=55&

Search result for term: "Italy"

Index: dlrprototype

Number of items: 20

The Copernicus Emergency Management Service - Flood in Alpes-Maritim Piedmont region, Italy | Copernicus

In the early hours of 3 October, an intense weather disturbance affected the Nk unprecedented rainfall and strong winds. Both red and orange alerts were issued by National Civil Protection. The Liguria region re

Metadata: language:eng, word count:879, index date:NaN-NaN-NaN NaN:NaN
Locations: Library • Italiano • Portugal • Chile • Alpes-Maritimes • Piedmont • Liguria • Europe • Cookies •

Keywords: floods • radar • sar • earthquakes •

<https://www.copernicus.eu/en/news/news/copernicus-emergency-management-france-flood-piedmont>

ESA - Contracts signed for three high-priority environmental missions

It marks the first time that Spain will lead the development of a Copernicus Sentinel-3 satellite carrying a high spatial-temporal thermal-infrared sensor to deliver observations o

Figure 2: The web interface of MOSAIC showing filters for geo-locations and keywords.

Integration of search results

In order to enrich search in digital libraries with web documents, an integration consisting of several steps has to be undertaken. First a web index has to be created consisting of web documents that are related to the digital library. The OpenWebSearch.eu project provides a technical infrastructure to create a web index that can be imported into MOSAIC. The specification of the web index is currently done by specifying a list of URLs of the web documents that should be included. In the future, the OWI will provide means to specify the content of an index with metadata, such as topic, language or domain.

The second step consists in the alignment of the joint metadata. This depends on the metadata that the digital library provides in its search API and the possibilities to integrate the same metadata into the web index and MOSAIC. For example, keywords used in a digital library might be structured according to a classification scheme. The keywords used in MOSAIC need to have the same structure. Thus, in a pre-processing step the web documents are analysed and tagged with keywords of the same classification scheme. Similarly, authors of publications can be extracted from web documents and tagged. Geographic information can be used as joint metadata if provided by the digital library.

In the third step a joint user interface has to be created that integrates the search over both the digital library and MOSAIC. A straightforward approach consists in the adaptation of the existing web interface of MOSAIC. While the built-in web interface queries the MOSAIC service, an additional query can be performed to a digital library. Thus, a federated search approach is realised. The web interface should then support the use of joint metadata implementing a kind of faceted search. For example, a keyword or author available in an item of the search result can be used for the new search query that retrieves results from both sources.

APPLICATION

The concept has been tried out in a use case in the field of Earth Observation (EO) and environmental search [7]. This use case includes a digital library of the German Aerospace Center (DLR) that contains publications in this research field. Furthermore, EO Catalogues are included that contain environmental information generated by satellites in the form of geographic maps. Items of these data sources are tagged with keywords and geo-coordinates. An integrated dashboard has been created that coordinates the search over these data sources and bundles the search results.

An index partition has been created that contains app. 500 news web pages related to natural disasters. This index has been integrated into MOSAIC and made available through the MOSAIC web service. The web documents are tagged with geographic information, namely coordinates of the mentioned locations in the documents. The dashboard of the application displays the search result of the web documents retrieved from MOSAIC (see Figure 3). This view also in-

cludes information of the contained locations and a button to show them in a map.

Figure 3: Search results of web pages retrieved from MOSAIC and displayed in the dashboard of the application.

The corpus of scientific publications included in the prototype application is provided by the German Aerospace Center (DLR). An internal snapshot of a scientific literature database which includes scientific publications in the domain of EO research has been imported into a Knowledge Graph Database. The initial data corpus is reduced in size (app. 12 000 documents) by filtering out non-relevant scientific publications that are not connected to the domain of natural disaster. In a pre-processing step keywords and authors are extracted from the raw attributes and added as explicit metadata of the documents. Thus, the Knowledge Graph can be queried by using search terms, but also keywords and authors. The search result is displayed in Figure 4 on the left side, where keywords and authors of each publication are highlighted.

The dashboard shown in Figure 4 displays query fields on top, the search results on the left side, and the map on the right side. The query fields accept general search terms, but also keywords and authors. The search result area on the left side includes three tabs to switch between the results of the three sources. By clicking on a keyword or author of an item in the search results, the respective word is automatically added to the query fields and used for a federated search over all sources. The map on the right side shows the locations of the results geographically. This map also enables to select a geographic area to filter the search.

The third information source of this application consists of geographical information coming from EO systems. Data is extracted from existing EO catalogues, such as Planetary Computer ¹ and Terrabyte STAC API ², and imported into the Knowledge Graph. These items contain metadata, such as title, keywords, origin, spatial extent, and time interval.

¹ <https://planetarycomputer.microsoft.com/>

² <https://stac.terrabYTE.lrz.de/browser/>

Figure 4: The Dashboard of the example application. The search fields are entered on top, the search results are displayed on the left side, and the locations of the search results are displayed on a map on the right side.

CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The main contribution of this paper consists in an approach to enrich search in a digital scientific library by adding web documents to the search result. Similar to a federated search approach, digital libraries and web documents are queried with search terms, keywords, geo-location, and other metadata. A semantic relation established through the same taxonomies of metadata is used to harmonise the search over different data sources. This approach brings the advantage to supplement past information of scientific publications with more recent knowledge, such as information of events, conferences, or research activities. In order to put this approach into practice, the software MOSAIC has been developed that allows to use indexed web data and integrate the search for metadata. The applicability of this approach is demonstrated with the example of an environmental search application.

Future work will include further development of the example application. Keywords will be structured to a taxonomy, so that the same set of keywords is used by all data sources. Second, focused crawling will be developed that allows to automatically create index partitions related to the science field.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101070014 (OpenWebSearch.EU, <https://doi.org/10.3030/101070014>).

REFERENCES

- [1] V.K. Sharma and S.K. Chauhan, “Digital library challenges and opportunities: An overview,” *Library Philosophy and Practice*, 2019. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/3725>
- [2] E. A. Fox, M. A. Gonçalves, and N. A. Kipp, “Digital libraries,” in *Handbook on Information Technologies for Education and Training*. 2002, pp. 623–641.
- [3] A. Tella, V. Okojie, and O. T. Olaniyi, “Social bookmarking tools and digital libraries,” in *Handbook of Research on Managing Intellectual Property in Digital Libraries*. 2018, pp. 396–409.
- [4] S. Gürtl, *MOSAIC: Empowering a Modular Framework for Configurable and Tailored Web Search based on an Open Web Index*, 2024. <https://diglib.tugraz.at/diplomaTheses>
- [5] M. Granitzer *et al.*, “Impact and development of an open web index for open web search,” *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology*, 2023. 10.1002/asi.24818
- [6] A. Nussbaumer, R. Kaushik, G. Hendriksen, S. Gürtl, and C. Gütl, “Conceptual Design and Implementation of a Prototype Search Application using the Open Web Search Index,” 2023. 10.5281/zenodo.10636166
- [7] J. Honeder, *Bridging Science and Web: An Open Search Application for Earth Observation and Environmental Research*, 2024. <https://diglib.tugraz.at/diplomaTheses>